

REDUCTION OF ACID POTASSIUM PERMANGANATE BY IODIDE, NITRITE AND BROMIDE

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Acid potassium permanganate may be quantitatively reduced to Mn^{2+} by iodide or nitrite when conditions are suitable ($N/10$ to $5N-H_2SO_4$); 5.0 and 2.5 moles of KI and KNO_2 respectively are required per mole of $KMnO_4$. On the other hand, reduction by KBr ($N/10$ to $2N-H_2SO_4$) stops short at the MnO_2 stage. The complete reduction to Mn^{2+} may perhaps be attained at 2 to $3N-H_2SO_4$, but further increase in acid concentration (up to $8N$) leads to evolution of oxygen and the consumption of KBr again drops steadily. In the KI titration of $KMnO_4$, there is an initial inflection at 0.5 mole KI, and in the KNO_2 titration, at 1.5 moles, but each of these shifts to larger amounts as the sulphuric acid concentration in the mixture is increased.

This work is in continuation of previous ones concerning oxidising properties of potassium dichromate, potassium iodate and other familiar oxidising agents (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 561; 1955, 32, 313; 1956, 33, 871; 1957, 34, 252; 1958, 35, 721). Although most of the potentiometric titrations described in these papers are familiar, the conditions of their satisfactory operation are not known in detail. It has been shown that in many of these titrations, the quantitative result may be completely upset if, for example, the acid concentration is not properly fixed. The same has again been observed with the permanganate titrations, which are described below.

Incidentally, we find that although the reduction of iodate by iodide or bromide, studied by Britton *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3877 *et seq.*), leads to similar results, the reduction of $KMnO_4$ by the same agents leads to quite different results.

The gradual reduction of $KMnO_4$ may take place in many ways. The main steps may be written down as follows :

Thus, in a titration with KI, for example, if all these reductions can be realised, one may expect inflections at 2, 3, 4 and 5 moles KI per mole $KMnO_4$. Many additional inflections are possible, e.g., if the available oxygen oxidises KI to KIO_3 .

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The experimental procedure has been fully described in a previous paper (*loc. cit.*, 1954). Generally 100 c.c. of $M/200-KMnO_4$ was taken in a titration vessel and the solution contained the desired amount of acid (H_2SO_4 or HCl). A bright

platinum foil electrode was used. $N/1$ solutions of KI, and $N/2$ solutions of KBr and KNO_3 were used for titration. Sufficient time was allowed for equilibrium to attain. No titration was completed in less than six hours.

Reduction by Iodide.—This reduction has been studied potentiometrically, perhaps, since 1921 by a number of workers. Hendrixon (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 14) detected only the final stage corresponding to reaction (4), i. e., 5 moles KI per mole $KMnO_4$ ($H_2SO_4 \sim 1N$). Kolthoff (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1921, 40, 552) used low concentrations of H_2SO_4 (0.2 to 0.5N) and was again able to detect only the final inflection. Müller and Möllering (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 151, 111) used 0.1N- H_2SO_4 and HCl solutions and were able to detect both reactions (4) and (5), the latter corresponding to half mole KI. These workers left the questions open whether other reductions could be detected in these titrations, and whether there were indefinite shifts in the locations of inflections observed. To investigate these matters the titrations were carried out in the following sulphuric acid media: (A) $N/10$, (B) $N/2$, (C) $N/1$, (D) 2N, (E) 3N, (F) 4N, G, 5N and (H) 6N. The corresponding titration graphs are shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

Titration of $M/200-KMnO_4$ (100 c.c.) with $N-KI$ in H_2SO_4 mixtures.

There are two inflections. The first is at first steady at half mole KI ($N/10$ to $N/1-H_2SO_4$), but at higher concentrations of acid it shows an increasing consumption of KI (0.66 mole at 2-3 N and 0.83 mole at 5-6 N). A dark brown precipitate appears with the first drop and increases during the titration, disappearing at the second inflection.

Fig. 2(a) shows the results when HCl replaces H₂SO₄ in the mixture, (A) N/30, (B) N/20, (C) N/10. The titration is not possible beyond N/10-HCl, as a perceptible odour of chlorine appears at that stage. The first inflection remains steady at half mole KI. The second inflection is at somewhat less than 5 moles and a little of the dark brown precipitate remains undissolved.

FIG. 2

(a). Titration of KMnO_4 with KI in HCl mixtures.
 (b). KMnO_4 with KNO_2 in HCl mixtures.
 (c). KMnO_4 with KBr in H_2SO_4 mixtures.

FIG. 3

Titration of 100 c.c. of $M/40\text{-KI}$ with $M/10\text{-KMnO}_4$ in HCl mixtures.

Fig. 3 shows the results obtained when these titrations were reversed. $M/40$ KI (100 c.c.) was taken in the cell and titrated with $M/10$ permanganate, acidified with HCl: (A) $N/10$, (B) $N/4$, (C) $N/2$, (D) $N/1$ and (E) $2N$. Since the permanganate delivered is preferentially consumed by KI, titration in $2N$ -HCl now becomes possible. When the acid is less than $N/2$, there is only one inflection at 0.2 mole $KMnO_4$ per mole KI. At higher concentrations of HCl, there is another inflection at 0.4 mole. Iodine precipitates out in the beginning, but dissolves towards the second inflection, disappearing completely at 0.4 mole $KMnO_4$.

Reduction by Nitrile.—The solutions used were $M/200$ - $KMnO_4$ (100 c.c. in the cell) and $0.463M$ - KNO_2 . The permanganate was acidified with HCl: (A) $N/30$, (B) $N/20$ and (C) $N/10$. The corresponding graphs are shown in Fig. 2(b). There are again two inflections as with KI, but the first one is at 1.5 moles, and the second at 2.5 moles KNO_2 . Fig. 4 shows the results in H_2SO_4 mixtures. The notable feature is that the first inflection at 1.5 moles KNO_2 shifts to higher values, when acid concentration is increased (1.8 at $5N \cdot H_2SO_4$).

FIG. 4

Titration of 100 c.c. of $M/200$ - $KMnO_4$ with $0.463M$ - KNO_2 in H_2SO_4 mixtures.

Reduction by Bromide.— $M/2$ -KBr was used (delivered from burette). The permanganate was acidified on the one hand with H_2SO_4 and on the other, with HCl: (A) $N/30$, (B) $N/20$, (C) $N/1$, (D) $2N$, (E) $3N$, (F) $4N$, (G) $5N$, (H) $6N$ and (I) $8N$. The graphs for sulphuric acid mixtures appear in Fig. 5 and those for HCl mixtures in Fig. 2(c). In weaker acid solutions up to $2N$, there is a single inflection at 3.0 moles KBr. At $3N \cdot H_2SO_4$ the inflection appears at 3.7 moles which increases

to 4.7 moles at 4*N* and thereafter decreases again (3.9 moles at 8*N*). Perhaps at an acid concentration, somewhere between 3*N*- and 4*N*-H₂SO₄, one may obtain a full reduction (inflection at 5.0 moles KBr). A special feature of titration with bromide is that some oxygen is evolved towards the end in strong H₂SO₄ solutions. The inflection remained steady at 3.0 moles in all the HCl solutions.

FIG. 5

Titration of 100 c.c. of *M*/200-KMnO₄ with *N*/2-KBr in H₂SO₄ mixtures.

DISCUSSION

When KMnO₄ is reduced, the *E*₀ is positive at all stages of reduction and, hence, the reduction is always spontaneous.

Some of the possible oxidations in the foregoing titrations are :

The E_0 's for these oxidations are negative so that they are not spontaneous. By combining the E_0 's suitably, one can get the following E.M.F.'s. for the complete cell reactions shown :

By multiplying these E_0 's by $23070 n$ one gets the corresponding decrease in free energy (cal. mole⁻¹). It is clear that there is no thermodynamic bar on the occurrence of reactions shown in (19) to (26). The equilibria in all cases are very favourable to completion of reduction. The poorest case appears in (23), but even here, $\log K = nE_0/0.059 = 6 \times 0.154/0.059$, whence $K = 4.58 \times 10^{15}$. In (20) similarly, $K = 2.63 \times 10^{27}$, a very complete reduction of permanganate indeed. In other cases the equilibrium constants have intermediate values.

In reductions by iodide, (20) shows the largest decrease in free energy, but is not observed to take place independently in any of the titrations so far. On the other hand, the corresponding reduction by bromide (24) is the only definite one in bromide titrations, 3 moles KBr per mole permanganate. Nitrite also produces this reduction, but only 1.5 moles of KNO_2 are consumed as is clear from the equation which has been set down above. It is clear that the reactions (19) to (26) are possible only in acid solutions, with the exception of (25).

In the reaction with KI, the decrease in free energy corresponding to (22) is quite distinct from that for (21). It should have been possible therefore to find

an inflection at 3.0 moles KI (0.5 for reaction 19 and 2.5 for reaction 22) and a final one at 5.0 moles. Only the latter of the two is observed in all titrations with KI. It appears therefore that the reduction after (19) may involve a mechanism by which one iodate and two MnO_2 molecules are simultaneously reduced by iodide. The inflection at 3.0 moles in the titration with bromide cannot be ascribed to the formation of bromate (reaction 23) followed by its reduction, since then, one would expect an initial inflection at 0.5 mole KBr .

Summarising, the reduction by KI in sulphuric acid solutions proceeds by the step (19), followed by (21) and (22) simultaneously. This is corroborated by the experimental observation that a dark brown precipitate (hydrated MnO_2) appears with the commencement of the titration and is followed by iodine only after 0.5 mole KI has been added. The filtrate at 0.5 mole KI on independent titration with KI requires 2.5 moles KI as expected, and the dark brown precipitate disappears at 5.0 moles KI, the mixture becoming practically colorless. These behaviours are unchanged in dilute hydrochloric acid solutions.

The first inflection in titrations with KI shifts to 0.66 mole in $N/2$ to $N/1$ - H_2SO_4 , and further to 0.84 mole in $5N$ to $6N$ acid. We were at first inclined to regard these shifts as an ill-defined approach to 1.0 mole KI. However, if the MnO_2 produced in (19) is at first reduced to Mn^{3+} and then to Mn^{2+} , and a corresponding quantity of iodide ions is oxidised to IO_3^- , it is easy to see that these shifts are quantitatively accounted for. This view is supported by the observation that the dark brown precipitate disappears before the final inflection (5 moles) in stronger sulphuric acid solutions.

When the titration is reversed and HCl is used in place of H_2SO_4 , the first inflection is at 0.2 mole KMnO_4 per mole KI which, of course, corresponds to complete liberation of iodine and reduction of MnO_4^- to Mn^{2+} . As the titration is continued further, the iodine precipitated at first redissolves and another sharp inflection is observed at 0.4 mole KMnO_4 . This corresponds to formation of ICl . In absence of excess KMnO_4 , at any stage the iodide ion is unable to get oxidised to iodate as in the previous experiments. With KNO_2 the inflections are steady in dilute HCl solutions (1.5 moles, 2.5 moles KNO_2). The final inflection obviously corresponds to

The shift observed in the first inflection (Fig. 5, H_2SO_4 mixtures) may again be ascribed to reduction of MnO_2 to Mn^{2+} , requiring half mole more of KNO_2 . However, the shift is always less than this.

The behaviour of KBr , when the permanganate contains dilute HCl , is again simple, the only inflection being at 3.0 moles KBr ; the reduction obviously follows reaction (24) since hydrated MnO_2 is formed and remains undissolved so that the final inflection corresponding to reduction to Mn^{2+} fails to appear. The behaviour in H_2SO_4 solutions is curious. Up to $2N$ - H_2SO_4 the reaction fulfills all the requirements of (24). At about $4N$ - H_2SO_4 , there must be an approach to full reduction

of the MnO_2 to Mn^{2+} , but the reaction is complicated by evolution of oxygen. It seems that the MnO_2 is first reduced to Mn^{3+} , a part of which produces oxygen,

(no consumption of bromide) and the rest is reduced to Mn^{2+} , consuming KBr

Since the iodide ion is far easier to oxidise to iodine than water to H^+ and oxygen, the evolution of oxygen is not observed in the titrations with KI .

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